

Ground State Quantum Oscillator and Lack of Information?

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The spatial and momentum wavefunctions of a ground state quantum oscillator are Gaussians in x and p respectively. A Gaussian is also the distribution which maximizes Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ for a fixed variance. Usually one would use average energy as a constraint, but for the nonrelativistic oscillator $KE = p^2/2m$ and $PE = .5kx^2$ so such a constraint is linked to the variance of x and p .

In this note we consider the following questions? Why is the ground state of the quantum oscillator (i.e. this form) the only quantum solution which matches a maximum entropy case (for a fixed variance)? Is there a link to a lack of information? Why do higher oscillator states represent non-maximum distributions for fixed variances? Can this also be linked to information? Here we apply the term information to actual information in the system not $\ln(P(i))$.

Gaussian as a Maximum Entropy Distribution for a Fixed Variance

Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ is often maximized subject to a constant average energy constraint i.e. $\sum_i e_i P(i)$. For an ideal gas in a box with no potential, $e_i = p_i^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic) so the constant energy constraint becomes a constraint on the variance ($\langle p^2 \rangle = 0$). This in turn leads to a Gaussian solution i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution :

$$P(p) = C_1 \exp(- p^2 / 2mT) \quad ((1))$$

If a potential is present $p^2/2m$ is replaced with $p^2/2m + V(x)$. In the case of an oscillator $V(x) = .5kx^2$. Thus one has a product of Gaussians i.e. maximum entropy for both p and x .

General Quantum Considerations

Quantum mechanics is associated with bound solutions of the time independent Schrodinger equation:

$$\{-1/2m \sum_p a(p) p^2 \exp(ipx)\} / \{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)\} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. with $a(p) = \text{momentum wavefunction}$.

Thus $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ are Fourier transforms of each other. One may ask: If either $W(x)$ or $a(p)$ is a Gaussian (i.e. a maximum entropy distribution for a fixed variance) can the other not be a Gaussian? The answer seems to be no because the Fourier transform of a Gaussian is a Gaussian. Thus either both $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ are both Gaussians or neither is a Gaussian.

A second question to ask is: If a certain state (say the ground state has Gaussians for $a(p)$ and $W(x)$), can higher energy states also have Gaussians?

Consider $W_n(x) = g(x)W_0(x)$ where n be any level. Then from ((2))

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} g(x) / g - 1/m \frac{dg}{dx} \frac{dW_0/dx}{W_0} = \Delta E \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } W_0 = \exp(-axx)$$

We assume $g = \exp(-bxx)$ so ((3)) yields:

$$-1/2m (-2b + 4bxx) - 4axx = \Delta E * m \quad \text{implying that } xx \text{ cannot cancel.}$$

Thus it seems that $g(x)$ cannot be a Gaussian. In other words one may have at most level with $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ as Gaussians.

Another question one may ask is why Gaussians are only solutions for the quantum oscillator case. We suggest that given the symmetry in the solutions for the ground state oscillator $W(x) = C_1 \exp(-.5axx)$ and $a(p) = C_2 \exp(-.5xx/a)$ one requires symmetry of $pp/2m$ and $.5kxx$ in the time-independent Schrodinger equation. If one uses the transformation:

$$X \rightarrow \sqrt{km} \quad xx = yy \quad \text{then} \quad -.5m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + .5kxx \quad \text{becomes} \quad -.5 \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} + .5yy.$$

In other words there is complete symmetry and it seems this symmetry is necessary for the two Gaussian solutions.

Information and Lack of Information?

It seems the ground state oscillator (or a solution in the form of this equation) is the only quantum one which may have $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ as Gaussians i.e maximum entropy distributions given a fixed variance. Is this result linked to information or a lack of information?

We try to argue it is. For the case of a symmetric equation $-.5pp + .5yy$ there is no bias between kinetic energy and potential energy for the ground state i.e. there is a complete lack of information in favour of one or the other. Thus $E = \langle KE \rangle + \langle PE \rangle$ with $\langle KE \rangle = \langle PE \rangle$. For other potentials the average kinetic energy and average potential energies may have a bias i.e. one carries more weight than the other and this is a type of information leading to less entropy. What about higher energy quantum oscillator states? They carry a bias or extra information because it is known they have more energy than the ground state. Thus it seems that only the quantum oscillator ground state has a complete lack of bias or a lack of information and so leads to a maximum entropy solution with fixed variances (as pp and xx) appear in the equation for energy so a constraint on energy is really one on pp and xx .

Conclusion

In conclusion we investigate why only the quantum ground state oscillator has $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ as Gaussian maximum entropy distributions for fixed variances. We argue that for such a maximum entropy situation one seeks a lack of information. First energy may be written as $.5pp + .5yy$ with $\sqrt{km}xx = yy$ so energy is written in terms of variances. Secondly, there is a

complete lack of bias or information between x and p for the oscillator potential. This suggests that the ground state oscillator may have a maximum entropy solution subject to a fixed variance. Higher energy states have a bias because it is known that they have more energy than the ground state- this is a form of information and we argue that extra information leads to less entropy.